

METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF INCREASING THE SPECIFICITY OF MEMORIZATION IN CHILDREN OF KIICHIK SCHOOL AGE

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Annotation. This article revealed the strengthening of methods of increasing the specificity of the memory process of preschool children through exercises.

Keywords: memory, thinking, process, will, Child personality, exercise, specialty, attention, interest long-term, stable, knowledge of the world around.

The upbringing of a harmonious personality is jaraoyyn, which is characterized by relevance. The proper organization of the psyche and physical development of children imposes great responsibility on the team of teachers.

Preschool age can occur only on the basis of volatility, volitional tension in the cognitive process of students, when, as such, the child seeks to fulfill the demand of those around him or act shahsively.

In the wellness of the psyche of a preschool child, it is possible to see the development of thinking in his cognitive activity. The child's Curiosity will be focused, mainly, on knowing the surrounding world, on learning. While playing, the elementary school student strives to be aware of the secret - synoats, causal events, and existence of the universe. For example, he himself can independently research what objects chuckle in water, and which ones swim. When a child is active in a mental relationship, he asks So many questions, and these questions are mostly diverse. The child is very interested in knowing the snow, how the rain falls, where the sun is at night, how the car walks, the distance from the earth to the sky. It was their "why?" "How?" "Through what?" will be aimed at getting answers to such questions. Children of this age are basically a deeper idea of what they are looking at

can walk. The main type of children's thinking at this age is figurative thinking. Education, which is given to children and is carried out mainly at school, is of paramount importance for the growth of children's thinking. For example, in the studies of the psychologist scientist Piaje, water mucus was applied from children 6-7 years old in containers equal to each other. The children replied that "the water in the pot is equal to the muck". It was the water in this muqdar that was poured before the eyes of the children into containers of different heights, and sungra said which container had the most water muqdar in which the children had the most amount of water in a thin but high container. The children were aware that their response was uncertain after seeing it in containers with exactly the same amount of water as each other. It was such an experiment that there were similar answers when plasticine images of the same size were changed and compared with buttons in a row, in which an equal number of buttons were poured more openly between them.

This experience proves that 6-7-year-olds mainly think about what they see. Education, which is given to children and is carried out mainly at school, is of paramount importance for

the growth of children's thinking. In the process of interrupting the knowledge given in education and school, with the growth of observability, memory and imagination, the range of things that will become material for the thinking of children of preschool age will expand, logical thinking and critical thinking will grow in children. In the process of education, the thinking of the child follows a great path of growth - from concrete thinking to abstract - feminine thinking.

In a child who is getting used to school training, attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable. In elementary school students, the opportunity to control attention with volitional tension and adapt to the situation will not be good. The main reason for this is the weakness and instability of voluntary attention in them. Involuntary attention in children will be more developed. The closeness, brightness, attractiveness of elementary grade educational materials, evoke involuntary feelings in the student and make it possible to master the basics of science without strong-willed tension. One of the distinctive features of the attention of students in grades 1-2 is that unig is not stable enough. Therefore, they cannot focus their attention on certain things for a long time and stay on objects of attention for a long time. The educational process creates favorable conditions for the development of voluntary, stable, strong, strong, active conscious attention of students of preschool age. In the process of obtaining knowledge, voluntary, conscious attention is formed in the process of Independent Mental Work, example - solving issues, performing exercises, repeating volitional exertion. In children of this age, the skill of collecting, organizing, distributing voluntary dictation, conscious fluency management begins to be formed. Below we will cite exercises that develop the memory process for Children of preschool age.

Exercise 1: Children are Read 6 pairs of words whose meanings are related to each other. For each pair suitable, the female otter must be chosen by the children.

Egg-Chicken Chick
Forest-Tree Board
Home-town street
River-lake sea
Coat-cold snow
Bird-Sky hive

Exercise 2. Exercises that develop associative memory.

Students are shown 10 cards with objects to remember. Children should simultaneously remember words that correspond to the content of the objects described on the cards.

Picture Cow Chicken book pen
Word milk Chick reading drawing
Picture vacuum cleaner needle fish
Word cleaning betting River
Picture Apple rose cake
Word garden whistle sweet

Exercise 3. Exercise "progress everything".

Objects of different sizes from 7 to 10 are poured into one row. (pictures with images of objects are also bulsa). Their top is covered. Then the 10th second is shown to the children by opening the top of the object and closing again. Children tell what they remember in the objects they see. Sungra is shown by opening the object column again from 8th to 1st second,

and from closing sung children are asked to tell the sequence in what order these objects are arranged. At the next stage, the position of the desired two objects is replaced and another 10 - second is displayed, and in children it is shown which objects are replaced.

At the next stage, it is proposed to tell their color regardless of the objects. Another option may be to find a subject that has “disappeared” from children.

Exercise 4. Children are Read 6 pairs of words whose meanings are related to each other. Children have to choose a third word for each couple that corresponds to its meaning.

Egg-Chicken Chick

Forest-Tree Board

Home-town street

River-lake sea

Coat-cold snow

Bird-Sky hive

Exercise 5. Finding encrypted 2-digit numbers verbally, keep them in mind.

MA BY YK OT SA PO

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
A	M	B	Y	K	O	S	I	P	T

Exercise 6. Children are given 5 encrypted words and their keys. Task: to find deciphered words, save them in memory, Mark words that do not correspond to their content.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
A	P	O	N	K	L	M	J	I	CH

2036 3011 2450 7810 590 (apple cherry fig pear saw)

Encrypt the words Apple, Cherry, fig, hok according to the given cipher.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	-
A	R	O	N	K	L	M	J	I	CH	

Exercise 7. Remembering word movements in pairs

Bloom opens drink

Red hot fast

Growth swim write sit

Barra large pen comfortable

In conclusion, it can be said that;

The results of the research of Russian psychologists confirm the opinion that various HIL yunalish, guidance is important to remember when mastering a material with a mano. Due to the fact that the first signal system is somewhat superior to the second signal system, students of preschool age are dominated by visual memory rather than logical memory. That is why they remember and remember, for a long time, more quickly and firmly, clear information, information, events and phenomena, images and things than theoretical laws and rules, abstract concepts.

The reader will have the opportunity to remember his own memory, conscious control, to make the processes of recall more appropriate for the purpose of his activity.

In the educational process of students of preschool age, effective recall plays a more important role than logical memory.

The process of memory at the age of preschool age is determined by the development of the process of perception, attention and thinking of students in them.

The productivity of voluntary recall and recall largely depends on the level of mental activity of students. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Second graders remember dry, not paying attention to the internal connections of the material, not understanding the manosi. They master superficially without the studied logical analysis. But the fact that they have a strong interest in different games is because giving educational material in the form of a game serves to improve their recall efficiency.

Fourth graders, on the other hand, pay attention to the internal connections of the material, understand the meaning and remember it logically. Even because they logically analyze the materials under study, the material is not mastered superficially. However, the interest in acquiring knowledge in them is not effective in remembering material that is not interesting to them, even because it is a state of attenuation in relation to second-graders.

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